

Women-led Startups in the Mental Healthcare: Ensuring Protection and Promotion of Mental Well-Being in India

Kunal Sinha¹ & Gauravkumar Talsaniya²

Abstract: *A person's mental well-being is linked to their collective and individual ability to think, emote, interact, earn, and enjoy; and therefore, the promotion, protection, and restoration of mental health is a vital concern for individuals, communities, and societies (WHO, n.d.). For centuries, women's roles have always been central to family well-being. Women's participation in education (especially in STEM), economic activities, and contribution to innovation and entrepreneurship directly influence children and family health, including mental well-being. However, their efforts to overcome the mental health challenges are not significantly recognized. The article draws attention to the following: (1) the significance of mental health; (2) the burden of mental illness across the globe, including India; (3) mental health challenges in India; and (4) women's role in mental healthcare startups. The arguments, statements, and analysis are based on the secondary data, including research papers, books, newspapers, and websites.*

Keywords: *Mental Healthcare; Women Empowerment; Startups; Healthcare Innovation; Mental Health Promotion*

Introduction

Background: Meaning and Significance of Mental Health

What constitutes health? Why has the term "well-being" gained significant traction over the past few decades? According to the World Health Organization (1948), health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being, not just the absence of disease or infirmity. This shift promotes a more inclusive and holistic understanding of health. The inclusion of "well-being" broadens the previously narrow interpretation of health and addresses the complexities and nuances associated with the term "health." In

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Studies in Science Technology and Innovation Policy (DSSTIP), School of Social Science, Central University of Gujarat, KUNDHOLA, Vadodara, Gujarat

² Research Scholar, Department of Studies in Science Technology and Innovation Policy (DSSTIP), School of Social Science, Central University of Gujarat, KUNDHOLA, Vadodara, Gujarat,

addition, the definition emphasizes that the protection and promotion of mental well-being are equally significant as physical health. It enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, effectively learn and work, and contribute to their community (WHO, n.d.).

Articulation of mental health is not a modern practice. Many ancient cultures across the world had diverse beliefs, principles, and opinions on mental well-being. For instance, ancient Egyptians believed that supernatural powers, such as demonic possession or sorcery, caused mental maladies. Their treatment included both participation in certain recreational activities (i.e., engaging in spiritual dances or body paintings) and the use of herbal remedies (Hunter, 2022). In ancient Greek philosophy, the individual is responsible for their health outcome. Taking care of one's health is considered an honourable act. Individuals carried out unique rituals founded on the principle of "Pan Metron Ariston," signifying moderation in all aspects. Here, the doctrine of moderation is interpreted as the ability to control oneself, one's feelings, and one's thoughts; it is the culmination of the path of knowledge and self-formation (Danylova et al., 2023). About the causation of mental illness, the people of ancient Greek society had diverse opinions, as some believed that it was a punishment of the gods while others considered it to be caused by physical and emotional problems (Adekannbi et al., 2018). This represents the interconnectedness of the mental and physical aspects of health.

In Indian philosophy, one can also find the essence of mental well-being. Numerous ancient Indian texts, statements, and beliefs highlight the relevance of the mind in overall well-being. These include: (1) the ultimate goal of life is self-realization or the understanding of one's inner self, and therefore material things are nothing but illusions; (2) one can gain knowledge not only through the external senses and logical reasoning but also through intuition and intense mental reflection; (3) philosophical insights are not merely abstract but have practical implications for enhancing overall well-being in life (Wig, 1989). Dr. N. C. Surya (the former director of the All India Institute of Mental Health, Bangalore, and one of the best-known Indian psychiatrists in recent years) defined a mentally healthy person as one who (1) is comfortable within himself (and thus has no mental illness or infirmity), (2) makes others around him comfortable (and thus is socially well adjusted), and (3) strives continually to evolve to higher spiritual levels (Surya, 1966; Wig, 1989).

Burden of Mental Illness—World and India:

If we look at the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) data, it appears that mental disorders across the globe ranked 7th as the leading cause of years lived with disability (YLDs) in 1990. And if we look at the status

of mental health in recent years, i.e., from 2016 to 2021, mental illness ranked 8th as the leading cause of YLDs. This indicates a lack of significant progress in safeguarding and enhancing mental health. In contrast, the contribution of mental disorders to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) shows a negative output when compared to the 1990 data. In the year 1990, mental disorder ranked 17th as the leading cause of DALYs, while from the year 2016 to 2021, it ranked 15th. This shows an urgent need to prioritize mental well-being and take necessary action as soon as possible. Sagar et al. (2020) articulated that mental disorders were the second-leading cause of YLDs and the sixth-leading cause of DALYs at the global level in 2017, posing a serious challenge to low- and middle-income countries' healthcare systems; therefore, mental health was recognized as one of the priority areas in health policies around the world, and it has also been included in the Sustainable Development Goals.

According to the GBD (1990), mental disorders in India ranked 13th as the leading cause of DALYs in the year 1990 and remained until the year 1997. In 1998, it dropped to the 14th rank and remained there for another year. In 2000, it fell further to the 15th rank, where it remained for another eleven years until 2011. This trend indicates a slow but at least steady and positive improvement. However, progress has not remained consistent. From 2012 to 2013, mental disorders ranked 14th as the leading cause of DALYs and were further ranked 13th until the year 2021. This indicates the negative output, particularly in light of major policy amendments initiated post-2014. These lead to two conclusions: India's mental health status and risk factors for mental disorders are slightly positive when compared to the global average, but not when compared to the country's own past health records.

Mental Health Challenges in India:

Almost one in five people in India are suffering from mental health conditions. It is incorrect to view mental health conditions as a rare health issue. However, a significant treatment gap persists, as roughly 85% of those affected are not receiving adequate care, which ultimately results in significant disability and impairment (Kar & Menon, 2024). We need to address the several mental health challenges described below.

I. Lack of Awareness and Misinformation:

In India, the ground-level barrier to accessing mental healthcare is a lack of awareness and misinformation about what constitutes mental well-being. There's a common misconception in society that if one does not have any sign of a mental disorder, it means one is mentally healthy. Mental health problems are often

associated with mental retardation or maniacal behaviour. Lakshmana et al. (2022) found the following result during their research on community perceptions of accessibility and barriers to utilizing mental health services: (1) The majority of participants could not express what normal mental health is as understood in literature; (2) they understood normal mental health as being free from mental illnesses; and (3) issues such as suicidal thoughts, adjustment problems, emotional issues, and sleep difficulties are not considered mental illness.

II. Stigma:

Stigmatizing mental health issues results in barriers to accessing quality care, increasing the probability of self-harm, and worsening the social and financial conditions of the diseased and their families. The stigma associated with mental health conditions appeared in three different levels: intrapersonal stigma, interpersonal stigma, and structural stigma. Intrapersonal stigma refers to the negative emotions and stereotypes that people with mental illness develop, e.g., shame, fear of judgements, and social isolation. The perception that people suffering from mental illness are crazy, weak, and self-responsible is an example of interpersonal stigma. And structural stigma means that policies, laws, healthcare practices, or social structures are unfair to people with mental health conditions (Javed et al., 2021).

III. Shortfall of Mental Healthcare Resources:

The National Mental Health Survey (NMHS) 2015-16 indicates that about 10.6 percent of the Indian adult population suffered from mental disorders. In addition, there was a significant treatment gap that ranged from 70 percent to 92 percent. Despite this, there has been minimal progress in expanding mental healthcare facilities. According to the Mental Health Atlas survey (2017), India has 136 mental hospitals and 389 psychiatric units per 100,000 populations. The number seems promising but not enough when considering the 1.4 billion populations. In 2017, there were 0.29 psychiatrists per 100,000 people. It was almost one-tenth of what the WHO suggested—three psychiatrists.

IV. Out-of-Pocket Expenditure:

The out-of-pocket (OOP) expenditure means a gap in patient payments—i.e., the difference between the amount charged for healthcare and what medicare and private health insurers pay (Rosenberg et al., 2022). Therefore, the amount patients and their families directly pay for healthcare services constitute out-of-pocket (OPP) expenditure. These include the costs of consulting, counselling, surgeries, medications, and other healthcare services. People often avoid or delay accessing mental healthcare due to high OPP. To

resolve this issue, the government made significant amendments to the policy, enacted laws, and introduced healthcare insurance in the last decade, e.g., the Mental Healthcare Act (2017), the National Mental Health Policy (2014), and the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY). By law, now private health insurers need to cover mental healthcare expenditures. However, there exists a loophole in the policy. For instance, government-provided insurance has certain limitations: the expenditure for psychiatric care is covered only if the patient is admitted to a government hospital; one cannot claim medication if it is prescribed by a private healthcare system; and the expenditure for counselling cannot be covered. In addition, most private insurance policies only cover in-patient expenses. Therefore, patients and their families need to pay the cost of outpatient care, psychotherapy, medication, and other non-medical services. Even government spending on mental healthcare is very low. It was only 1.30 percent of the total health expenditure (Mental Health Atlas, 2017). All these factors contribute to an increase in OPP expenditure.

Women's Contribution to Family and Society:

Traditionally, women were assigned roles, mostly confined to household responsibilities and care, ranging from cooking and cleaning to family care. Women's participation in the social, educational, and economic spheres is negligible compared to men. The belief was that women were, by birth, weaker, less intellectual and irrational. Thanks to the feminist and other social movements of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, women can work and learn, contributing to scientific and technological innovation and research, and participate in politics.

However, these have not changed much today, particularly in underdeveloped and developing countries. For instance, cleaning and maintaining the home, cooking the food for the family, raising the child, and taking care of the elderly members of the family are the primary responsibilities of women. Not only this—in some cultures and societies, women's personal and social characteristics, dignity, and status (in their own home and community) are evaluated based on how well they are determined and obliged towards these responsibilities. Yes, society is advanced and women have the right to participate in all social, economic, and political activities, but not (at least socially) at the cost of their primary household and family care.

Regarding the women's contribution to healthcare, they are supposed to provide basic care and daily assisting services to their family members. These include hygienic care, monitoring and feeding nutritious food, medication management, supporting basic symptom monitoring, providing emotional support, and communicating with healthcare professionals. Surprisingly, all this work is often unpaid, less valued and regarded as informal care, even though many scholarly works articulate that women hold a dominant

position in formal caregiver roles such as nursing, counselling, and supportive care. According to The Commonwealth Fund blog (2024), about 81% of caregivers for the elderly population across the world are women. Yes, it is informal care (in terms of the biomedical model and practice). However, according to a holistic understanding of health and practice, all these activities are equally significant, considering the value they add to the actual healthcare.

Women-led Startups in Mental Healthcare:

Mental health impacts an individual's overall well-being as well as a country's social, economic, political, and environmental ecosystem. Almost one in 10 Indians suffers from mental health conditions. Given this, the government has already taken the necessary steps. However, there are still numerous challenges that impede access to equitable and quality mental healthcare. These include challenges associated with social stigma, outreach, affordability, resource availability, and research and development.

The role of women in New India extends to significant participation in education (including STEM), research & development, innovation, and entrepreneurship. As a result, women-led startups have the potential to enhance the quality, affordability, and accessibility of mental healthcare. As a result, women-led start-ups has potential to enhance mental healthcare landscape by (1) creating non-stigmatized and inclusive spaces; (2) focusing on holistic mental healthcare; (3) contributing to technology and healthcare; and (4) understanding and valuing the caregiver's well-being. Figure 1 shows the key women-led startups in India.

Figure 1: Women-led Startups in Mental Healthcare

Company	Year of Incorporation	Founder	Services Provided	Features	Target Audience
ePsyClinic	2015	Shipra Dawar (Founder & CEO)	Custom-made therapy and counselling	Online assessment; Connect with counselling therapist, psychotherapist, psychoanalytic, and consultant	Individual, Families and Corporate
Wysa	2015	Jo Aggarwal (Co-founder & CEO)	Personalized mental healthcare including 24/7 remote support, self-care tools, and connect to therapists and psychiatrists	AI-enabled automated assessment, CBT tools, and risk detection; 24/7 Digital psychosocial support; Electronic Health Records; and Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM), Chronic Care Management (CCM) and Collaborative Care Model (CoCM)	Children and Young People, Adults, Healthcare Providers, Mental and General Healthcare Organizations

Trijog	2014	Anureet Sethi (Director and Chairperson); Arushi Sethi (Co-founder & CEO)	Adult counseling, child counseling, and corporate wellness	Online Screening; Digital personalize assistance; Network of RCI registered therapists and certified psychologists	Children, Adolescents, Adults and Corporates
YourDOST	2014	Richa Singh (Co-founder)	Student wellness, career counseling, and suicide prevention; Employee engagement and culture compass; and parenting courses, shadow services for the child and faculty development program	24/7 Psychologists Services, remote therapy sessions, and networking of 1000+ qualified healthcare experts	Corporates, College, and Schools
Amaha (formally named InnerHour)	2016	Neha Kirpal (Co-founder) joined in 2019	Adult therapy and psychiatry; tailor-made child mental healthcare; couple therapy; and self-care	Offer both-online and in-person mental healthcare; psychometric assessments; ongoing monitoring and support system; electronic health records; and data transparency and security	Children, Adult, Colleges, and Corporate

Source: Secondary Data

Compilation: Author

Conclusion

Protection and promotion of mental well-being require a comprehensive approach encompassing psychiatric care, therapy, counselling, and caregiving. Historically, women have predominantly been associated with household responsibilities, as well as child and elderly care—roles that continue to persist in contemporary society. They also play a crucial role in formal caregiving. However, they receive comparatively less pay and recognition. Women turn all these challenges into opportunities and continue to excel. Gradually, they increased their participation in the STEM, healthcare, and psychological fields. Additionally, the government's incentives and support encouraged women to start their own mental healthcare startups. It empowered the women to be financially independent, decision-makers, and leaders in their respective fields.

We can conclude that the growing entrepreneurial spirit and leadership demonstrated by women in mental healthcare yield significant impacts, including (1) de-stigmatizing mental illness and making the public aware of what mental well-being means; (2) enhancing the outreach of mental healthcare; (3) improving the affordability, accessibility, and quality of mental healthcare; (4) valuing and availing all kinds of mental healthcare, such as psychotherapy and counselling; (5) empowering women by facilitating social and economic independence; and (6) ensuring women's and their families' mental well-being.

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